

CoMSES Digest: Summer 2025

Volume 13, No. 2 March 16th - June 15th, 2025

Editor's Note

I am thrilled to write to you all as a third-time re-elected member of the CoMSES Executive Board. I gladly accept this position with humility, sense of responsibility, and appreciation for my peers' recognition to continue supporting our community. While I'm deeply honored, it is also important to ensure that there is room for new perspectives and initiatives, and I encourage you all to put your names forward to be part of the CoMSES leadership.

One aspect I'd like to reinforce during my new (fourth!) term is the important role we play beyond our scientific community. We are modelers and co-creators of critical knowledge about socio-ecological systems that we seek to positively influence. But more importantly, we are also global citizens. Three years ago, I wrote my first guest-editor note for CoMSES with a call to action: "I urge you to get involved and put your SES science and modeling expertise to the service of democracy, worldwide." While back then I could recognize the trends, I could not—nor did I want to, perhaps—anticipate how prescient my writing would be, how unequivocally the trend would play out. My concern did not arise from any form of divination or existential anxiety; it was informed by our very own collective SES modeling. The writing has been on the wall for at least 40 years, but we have severed ourselves from the very human, social, and political system that we are part of in the quest for objectivity and rationality.

We cannot be objective—ever—because we are subjects, not objects. Biases are inherent in our work; we can only be aware, honest and transparent about them, and understand their potential effects on the outcomes we seek. That pursuit of scientific objectivity—also known as basic science—has frequently translated into a greater esteem for (natural) sciences and quantitative modeling relative to other forms of knowledge that may be equally valuable. While science can protect us from charlatans and propaganda (as Carl Sagan, who I quoted three years ago, warned us), perhaps it is time to reflect on how we have isolated ourselves and our modeling and scientific practice from the rest of society. Science—the process of systematic inquiry—is just one of many social processes, with goals, rules, norms, and practices that must adapt to a changing world. If we cannot humbly recognize the relativity of scientific knowledge, we will only perpetuate the mistrust in science that we currently experience and that make our societies more vulnerable to poor decisions and their disruptive consequences.

What does this mean in practice for our community? Let us redefine what SES modeling is for and how it can be done to better serve the world, towards the

stability and longevity of the socio-ecological systems that we are committed to. There are exciting initiatives that CoMSES is spearheading to support this, including the collaboration with CSDMS (Community Surface Dynamics Modeling System), grant proposals that we hope to secure to make our CoMSES modeling accessible to decision-makers, the efforts to advance FAIR modeling principles and Open Science initiatives, to name a few. This is the time to support everyone's efforts and amplify them through our professional networks, yes, but also to engage as citizens, wherever we are in the world, contributing with our vote, our voice, and our modeling for better local, regional, national and global decision-making.

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CoMSES.Net Summer Issue Guest Editor

CoMSES News

Recent Meeting & Workshop Activity

We're The CoMSES Net team has had a busy and productive second quarter. In April, Allen Lee and Scott Foster hosted the 2nd [SciCodes Collaboration Workshop](#) in Washington DC, bringing together editors and maintainers from a wide range of scientific software registries and repositories as well as open research software practitioners and advocates to advance research software in three focal areas:

1. [Best practices for research software registries and repositories](#): facilitating adoption of and revisiting our published best practices
2. Metadata engineering: exposing [curated, interoperable software metadata](#) to support novel downstream use cases including federated search, and emerging LLM augmentations
3. Research software quality: helping research communities adopt FAIR4RS and frictionless software engineering practices

The workshop was preceded by a half day symposium, "Building the Future of Research Software", where Dr. Katherine Skinner, program director at [Invest in Open Infrastructure](#), delivered a timely keynote covering key points from IOI's [comprehensive landscape analysis on open research software infrastructures](#). One key takeaway from the keynote was the critical need for scholarly infrastructures to prepare, streamline and invest in coordination and collaboration across open scholarly infrastructures. To that end, Allen Lee is coordinating efforts as co-chair of the [SciCodes Consortium](#) to support how our registries and repositories expose curated, standardized metadata for discovery, search, and novel downstream use cases like LLMs, which will be discussed in more detail in a future digest. A SciCodes working group was also established, led by Alice Allen from the Astrophysics Source Code Library to revisit the SciCodes best practices for research software registries and repositories and focus on resilience and disaster recovery (e.g., how easy would it be to spin up and restore a working copy of the metadata and data that model authors so diligently provided to the CoMSES Model Library?).

In May, Allen Lee and staff research software engineers Anton Suharev, Scott Foster ran a clinic at the CSDMS 2025 Annual Meeting (cheekily titled “Get Lazy with LLMs”) that drew a full house. Slides are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15741397> with an accompanying GitHub repository that we hope will continue to serve as a useful stepping stone for learning about LLMs available at <https://github.com/comses-education/get-lazy-with-llms-clinic> . We welcome more contributions from the community to advance how we can ethically and effectively use LLMs in our work! Anton Suharev has been diligently exploring the potential for LLMs to augment the CoMSES Model Library, with additional assistance from Sean Bergin, Manuela Vanegas-Ferro, as well as the rest of the team. We hope to have preliminary prototypes to share with the rest of the community by the end of the year, and believe that in spite of the hype and ecological costs LLMs have the potential to offer transformative benefits for the kinds of computational modeling.

Scott Foster and student workers Charles Sheelam and Karthik Bandagonda have also been diligently working to refresh the CoMSES Science Gateway’s landing page and make it easier to surface hidden areas of the site and community contributions. Some elements are already live, others are but a few short weeks away. As always if you have any concerns or feedback, [please let us know](#) - especially welcome is feedback on the new landing page and associated Gateway updates.

Keep Your CoMSES Profile Updated

Please consider keeping the CoMSES community informed by updating your user account on CoMSES Net! Let fellow researchers and modelers get to know you by including a biography, research interests, and/or institutional affiliation. [Click here](#) to edit your profile and while you are at it, why not link your account to GitHub and ORCID!

As always, feel free to join the conversation by visiting the [Forums tab](#), or by starting a discussion on a specific model, event, or job posting. If you register your affiliation on your profile page, it will help us fill out our new member profile map: <https://www.comses.net/about/metrics/>!

Calendar of Events

Follow the links to the local event organizers for the latest information or go to <https://comses.net/events/> for a listing of all recent events. You can also subscribe to new events by following us on [Twitter/X](#) or subscribing to our [RSS feeds](#).

Upcoming Deadlines

[The 2025 International Conference of the Computational Social Science Society of the Americas \(CSSSA\)](#)

Dates: November 6-9, 2025; Submission Deadline June 30, 2025

Call for Participation for the 2025 Computational Social Science Society of the Americas (CSSSA) conference, which will be held in Santa Fe this November. It’s a great little conference—intimate (single track), interdisciplinary, and full of

interesting work from people using CSS methods in a wide range of contexts. CSSSA has been running this conference for nearly 20 years and it consistently draws a vibrant, engaged community.

The CSSSA defines computational social science broadly as the theory-driven application of computational methods to analyze, model, and simulate social systems. This includes analyzing large-scale social data, exploring mechanisms underlying social dynamics through simulation, and connecting insights to social science theory.

We especially encourage submissions that address applied Computational Social Science or demonstrate its real-world impact. CSSSA is an inclusive organization, welcoming contributions from all researchers regardless of background or institutional affiliation. Submissions are evaluated exclusively on scientific merit, relevance, and potential impact on the field.

24th Asia Simulation Conference (AsiaSim 2025)

Dates: November 17-19, 2025; Submission Deadline July 13, 2025

AsiaSim (Asia Simulation Conference), 24th in the series, is an annual international conference organized by the Federation of Asia Simulation Societies (ASIASIM) whose current member societies are China Simulation Federation (CSF), Japanese Society for Simulation Technology (JSST), Korea Society for Simulation (KSS), Society for Simulation and Gaming of Singapore (SSAGsg) and Malaysian Simulation Society (MSS). The Federation of Asia Simulation Societies (ASIASIM) was set up to promote the advancement of modelling and simulation in industry, research and development in Asia and beyond.

The AsiaSim conference is an international forum for disseminating recent advances in modeling, simulation and gaming. AsiaSim provides a meeting place for simulation researchers and practitioners in all disciplines in academic, industry, government sectors among others to share leading developments and advances in systems simulation.

Model Library

Newly Reviewed

5 models passed CoMSES's [peer review process](#) this quarter!

CoMSES is always looking for new model reviewers! As such we welcome your self nomination. If you would like to join our reviewer network, we invite you to do so by creating a peer reviewer profile under "Edit Profile" on your comses.net account.

New Model Uploads

Twenty new models were published in the [CoMSES Model Library](#) on a wide variety of topics that illustrate the depth and breadth of our community. These include:

- Evaluating the influence of social, political, and environmental factors on [Urban Transport Mode Choices](#)

- Simulating the [Development of coral reefs under climate change](#)
- Investigating strategies to address [Finance and Market Concentration Using Agent-Based Modeling](#)
- Modeling the impacts of vegetation and rainfall on the [spatio-temporal distribution of Sahelian transhumant herds](#)

These models and more can be discovered at the [CoMSES Model Library](#) - you can also keep up-to-date with newly published models on our [Twitter/X](#) and [RSS](#) feeds.

Most Downloaded Models

1. [Fertility Tradeoffs](#) by Kristin Crouse (244 downloads)
2. [The Hawk-Dove Game](#) by Kristin Crouse (210 downloads)
3. [An Agent-Based Model of Indirect Minority Influence on Social Change](#) by Jiin Jung (85 downloads)
4. [Virus Transmission with Super-Spreaders](#) by J M Applegate (26 downloads)
5. [Deforestation](#) by Mohammad Ali Aghajani (16 downloads)

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CoMSES Net is headquartered in
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